

Hacking Life

HOW TOKENIZATION AND RECREATIONAL NFT COLLECTION OFFERINGS MAY CHANGE THE FUTURE OF INDUSTRIAL MINING AND ARCHAEOLOGICAL PROJECT FUNDING VIA ENHANCEMENT OF LIQUIDATION RATIO

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INTRODUCTION

Cryptocurrency and blockchain projects, which shine as an alternative investment channel especially in the bottleneck in which the world economy has entered due to the Covid-19 Pandemic, tend to lose their old credibility due to the recent turbulent activity.

The asset values of cryptocurrencies are mainly based on two elemental factors. The first element is the nominal asset value and the anonymity of transfers, the second is the volume size and volatility of the cryptoassets involved. Today, aggressive KYC (Know Your Customer) protocols, which have been recently imposed by the states to eliminate the anonymity of cryptocurrencies, suppress the most important privilege of these assets to be the primary investment tool. Other daily volume and money-making volatility factors turn into neutral at best and sometimes negative in the absence of the first element.

The commonly accredited means to prevent this and ensure that cryptoassets remain as a reliable investment tool is the establishment of stable coins with fixed value or amount.

Tokenization of both prospecting & operating mining licenses along with the finalized metallic products & finalized industrial materials in countries like Turkey with large IV Group mining potential within the framework of stable coin projects ;accompanied with a well-established legal infrastructure that will protect the investor in the widest scope seems destined to serve as a novel method of liquidation with regards to ore mining with unprecedentedly high levels.

First examples of the aforementioned tokenization projects with a gold field in MENA Region are about to be initiated.

Along with potential foreign investor attraction, tokenization projects may serve as a permanent salvation for many valuable IV Group Mining Enterprises that have been idle from current financial difficulties.

3D MODELLED ARCHAEO-NFT COLLECTION OFFERINGS TO CONVERT EXCAVATION PROJECTS INTO SELF-FUNDING INITIATIVES

Non-fungible tokens certify that a digital asset is one-of-a-kind (authenticity) and define its ownership; digital unique phenomena that can be defined as your digital signature on a work. NFTs cannot be copied or replaced with another NFT as they undergo cryptographic operations. This unique record is kept in a digital ledger on the blockchain and can be accessed by anyone who has the code.

A new perspective on NFT projects, which also attract great attention in MENA and European region, is formed by the rapid development of 3D printing techniques. So much so that recently, the idea of transforming the identical models of rare historical artifacts into unique NFT collections by structuring them with 3D printing technology has started to be implemented in the world. As one of the recent examples of an identically re-modelled archaeological collection, which consists of approximately 400 pieces of ancient coins, statues, rings and medallions from the Roman period, is currently undergoing Archaeological NFT tokenization by a commodity based investment bank in Kosovo.

It is stated that the probable value of the European collection, whose owners are kept secret, is 1200 Bitcoin (approximately \$ 47 million). Musa Karademir, the chairman of BDU International, who received the exclusive curation and marketing rights of the collection for 3 years stated that: “The curation authority of this NFT collection, which consists of the world's first 3D recreational antique commodity models, was given to our company by the owners, by invitation. As a team, we will continue to work in a way that deserves this honor and trust.”

Stating that he believes the idea of 3D recreational modeling will pave the way for both the protection of historical artifacts and the ability of archaeological studies and museums to fund themselves, Karademir stated that he thinks that NFT-based certification methods can play a very active role in preserving historical artifacts in the future.

Stating that a comprehensive report explaining the exhibition and curation strategies of the collection has been prepared, Karademir informs that the related report will be submitted to the approval of the observation committee formed by the collection owners and collection sponsor Spektral Investment Bank board members Erdal Can Alkoçlar and Metehan Yeşil on May 15. Making a statement on the subject, Erdal Can Alkoçlar and Metehan Yeşil said: “This joint model, where 3D printing technologies combined with the reliability of NFT blockchain, effectively paves the way for self-funding of museums and exhibition projects that have difficulty in finding investors in developing countries, as well as potential future validation methods for artworks. It is diversifying in an unprecedented way.”

SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY PROJECTS TO POTENTIALLY BENEFIT FROM ARCHAEO-NFT OFFERINGS

Musa Karademir also said that with a significant portion of the income to be obtained from the sale of the relevant NFT collection, they will prioritize projects which are jointly carried out by the BDU Diplomatic Association and the United Kingdom's Organization for Peace and Development in Europe as well as projects with high social contributive value, such as Meryem Boz Sports Academy, led by renowned Olympic Turkish National athlete Meryem Boz which will bring forth the female athlete potential of Turkey. Established under the leadership of Boz and accompanying management team Gözde Yorgun & Merve Gülaç, the sports academy has the distinction of being the first Turkish sports academy modeled to evolve into a professional sports club and designed primarily to have an infrastructure to favor female athletes. Karademir also informed that they are in talks with several foreign NFT exchanges regarding the sale of the NFT collection, adding that they plan to launch an NFT exchange that would be supervised by Spektral Holding CTO Abdullah Mazlum who led a number of successful blockchain projects where only recreational NFTs will be sold in the near future.

Based on above mentioned improvements and enterprises, it is evident that both tokenization of mining licenses and industrial raw materials and Archaeological NFT offerings based on identical 3D re-modelling of actual collectionized artifacts, will serve as novel yet effective means of asset liquidation and convert seemingly static commodities into dynamic crypto-assets, possibly serving as a functional adjunctive factor for re-mobilizing the stagnated global economy due to prolonged Covid-19 pandemic.